

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees in Tirunelveli with Special Reference to Motivational and Demotivational Factors

C.PRIYA

Ph.D(Commerce)Scholar

Register No:19111191012002

**Sadakathullah Appa College (Autonomous),
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University,
Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012,TamilNadu,India**

Dr.P.GEETHA

Supervisor

Assistant Professor of Commerce

**Sadakathullah Appa College (Autonomous),
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University,
Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012,TamilNadu,India**

ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction is the foremost and most important factor for all the employees working in an organization as well as for the organization. It can be developed through the improvement of skills and refinement of knowledge for the employee and the inputs given by each employee and their increase output for their business concern. From this study we can observe the effect of motivational factors and positive work environment which affects bank employees of Tirunelveli district. Some of the motivational factors attributing to development of confidence level of employees are good relationship among employees, handling currency, job rotation and personal growth. Work environment plays an important role in influencing job satisfaction.

Implementation of safety measures, grievance redressal mechanism form a major part of work environment. Therefore all employees can have an opportunity to develop their own skills and ideas to improve their efficiency level and by giving motivation each and every employee can show their inbuilt talent to the organization.

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction is the level of contentment a person feels regarding his or her job. This feeling is mainly based on an individual's perception of satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be influenced by a person's ability to complete required tasks, the level of communication in an organization, and the way management treats employees. Job satisfaction is a worker's sense of achievement and success on the job. It is generally perceived to be directly linked to productivity as well as to personal well-being. Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction has been defined in many different ways by researchers. Some believe it is simply how content an individual is with his or her job, in other words, whether or not they like the job or individual aspects or facts of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the demographic factors of sample respondents those are working at banks in Tirunelveli district.
- To evaluate the motivational factors leads to job satisfaction of employee and their effect on productivity.
- To analyze the work environment of bank employees of the sample population.

Review of Literature

Esra, Z. (2012) concluded that employees should be awarded in such a way to give motivation for their better performance. By doing this research author had explained banks have follow some HRM practices in order to have a good relation among employees such as giving training, facing new challenges, performance appraisal, career planning, reward and potential appraisal.

Singh (2009) evaluated the effect of motivational practices of HRM and organization culture resulting in good work environment among various public sector and private sector banks. Results revealed that the HRM practices and positive work environment among employees were strong symbols of growth and improved job satisfaction levels among both private and public sector bank employees

3. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- This study is limited to the persons employed in banks in Tirunelveli district.
- This statistical study has its base from 104 randomly collected samples from respondents currently under employment among various banks in Tirunelveli district.
- Primary data has been collected through Direct Questionnaire.

4. METHODOLOGY:

4.1 Type of research

- The project is of the descriptive research model. Descriptive research studies are those studies, which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual, or of a group. In this study the awareness of the bank employees of Tirunelveli city were studied.
- This section attempts to describe the methodology of the present study. It includes sampling techniques, collection of data and tools of analysis of data.

4.2 Sampling Technique

Simple random sampling technique was used for collecting the primary data. I tried to cover almost all parts of Tirunelveli city.

The data needed for the project consists of:

- a) Primary data
- b) Secondary data

Primary data -collected from primary sources by using a schedule of questionnaire consisting of question. Simple random sampling has been applied for data collection.

Secondary data - collected from books, reports, journals and websites. Only supportive secondary data has been included.

4.3 Statistical tools for analysis

- Tabulation
- Percentage

- Mean score analysis
- F Test

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 5.1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S No	Demographic Factors	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	62	59.6
		Female	42	40.4
2	Qualification	Professional	12	11.54
		Degree Holder	60	57.7
		Post Graduate	28	26.93
		Others	4	3.85
3	Age Group	21-30 Years	43	41.35
		31-40 Years	39	37.5
		41-50 Years	15	14.43
		Above 50 Years	7	6.7
4	Experience Level	Less than 6 months	6	5.77
		6 months – 2 years	38	36.54
		2 – 5 Yrs	48	46.16
		More than 5 years	12	11.54
5	Income Group	Upto Rs.10,000	8	7.77
		Rs.10,001 to Rs.20,000	40	38.47
		Rs.20,001 to 30,000	26	25
		Above Rs.30,000	30	28.8

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 5.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. The above table confirms that out of 104 respondents, 62 (59.6%) of Bank employees are male and 42 (40.4%) of bank employees are female. In case of qualification, 4 respondents (3.85%) has done other studies, 12 respondents (11.54%) have completed their diploma, 28 respondents (26.93%) have completed their post graduation while 60 respondents (57.7%) have completed their graduation. Among age group of respondents, 5 respondents (4.81%) belong to the age group below 20 years, 43 respondents (41.35%) belong to the age group of 21-30 years & 34 respondents (32.7%) belong to the age group of 31- 40 years. 15 respondents (14.43%) belong to the age group 41 - 50 years, 7 respondents (6.77%) belong to the age group of above 50 yrs. From the point of view of experience, 48 respondents (46.16%) have a work experience between 2 – 5 years in the current bank, 38 respondents (36.54%) have around 6 months – 2 years in their current job, 12 respondents (11.54%) have spent more than 5 years while only 6 respondents (5.77%) have spent only 6 months in their current assignment. 8 respondents (7.77%) reported income level up to 10000/-, 30 respondents (28.8%) reported their monthly income above 30000/- , 26 respondents (25%) reported their monthly income from 20000/- to 30000/- and 40 respondents (38.47%) reported their family income from 10000/- to 20000/-. According to this table 4% of employees are having experience of less than 6 months, 24% of respondents are having experience of 6 months to 1 year, 34% of respondents are having 2- 5 years of experience level, majority of respondents 38% are having more than 5 years of experience level.

Table 5.2 Motivational factor of Respondents

Sl.No.	Motivational Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	Facing new challenges	40	38.47
2	New RBI policies	12	11.54
3	Handling currency	20	19.25

4	Accounting	20	19.25
5	Job Rotation	12	11.54
	Total	104	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is understood that out of 104 respondents, 40 respondents (38.47%) reported that facing new customers motivates them daily, 12 respondents each (11.54%) reported new RBI policies and job rotation as motivational factors while 20 respondents each (19.25%) reported handling currency and accounting as their motivational factors. Therefore most of the respondents are motivated at the thought of facing new customers.

Table 5.3 Motivation for better performance

Sl. No.	Prominent features	Income group			Total	F Statistics
		Low	Middle	High		
1	Involvement & responsibility among employees	3.23	3.46	3.25	3.29	1.25
2	Feeling of security	3.98	4.02	3.68	3.83	2.79
3	Personal growth	3.65	3.8	3.42	3.6	0.48
4	Pleasant work environment	3.69	3.58	3.08	3.52	2.97
5	Recognition for creativity	3.53	3.45	3.28	3.42	0.98

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table indicates that among various motivational factors for better performance feeling of security is the most prominent feature for bank employees among all income groups with an overall mean of 3.83. And also middle income group respondents' scored 4.02. Personal growth also scored high as motivation with a mean of 3.6 across all income groups. Pleasant

work environment & recognition for creativity rank high among income groups as motivational factors for bank employees with mean values of 3.52 & 3.42.

H₀₁ : There is no significant difference among different income group and motivation for better performance

The above hypothesis has been tested in the light one way Anova. The results are given in table no.5.3. It can be concluded from the above table that framed null hypothesis has been rejected in case of feeling of security and pleasant work environment. In case of Involvement & responsibility among employees, personal growth and recognition for creativity the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus it is concluded that there is a significant difference among income group people on the motivation for better performance from feeling of security and pleasant work environment.

Based on the mean score and F-test results the employees still need recognition for creativity and personal growth and involvement & responsibility among employees.

Table 5.4 Factors affecting work environment

Sl. No	Aspects	Income Group			Mean score	F Statistics
		Low	Middle	High		
1	Psychological stress and frustration	3.42	3.42	3.34	3.39	.678
2	Grievance Redress mechanism	3.08	2.92	3.2	3.06	.257
3	Physical inabilities including health problems	3.04	3.2	2.8	3.32	.718
4	Safety measures provided by bank	3.18	3.24	3.22	3.21	.344
5	Challenging work nature in the job	3.42	3.3	3.42	3.36	.029
6	Social Status in the society	3.25	3.28	3.45	3.32	.105

Source: Computed Primary Data

Table 5.4 summarizes that among prominent factors affecting work environment among bank employees psychological stress and frustration is the most dominant factor that affects work environment with a mean value is 3.39, with mean values of 3.42 among low and middle income groups. Among low income groups, challenging work nature in the job also has a mean value of 3.42 equaling it as a dominant factor affecting work environment among low income group people. Social status in the society is the most dominant factor affecting work environment among high income group people with a mean value of 3.45.

H₀₂ : There is no significant difference among different income group and factors affecting work environment

The above hypothesis has been tested in the light one way Anova. The results are given in table no.5.4. It can be concluded from the above table that framed null hypothesis has been rejected in case of psychological stress and frustration, physical inabilities including health problems and safety measures. In case of grievance redress mechanism, challenging work nature in the job and Social Status in the society the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus it is concluded that there is a significant difference among income group people on the factors affecting work environment from psychological stress and frustration, physical inabilities including health problems and safety measures provided by bank.

Findings

- ✓ 59.6 percent of the respondents are male
- ✓ 57.7 percent of the respondents are Degree Holders
- ✓ 41.3 percent of the respondents belong to the age group between 21- 30 years.
- ✓ 38.7 percent of the respondents earn between Rs. 10000/-and Rs. 20000/- per month.
- ✓ 46.1 percent of the respondents have been employed between 2 to 5 years in their current organization.
- ✓ 38.4 percent of the respondents believe facing new customers is their highest motivational factor.

- ✓ Feeling of security is the most preferred motivational factor for better performance among bank employees across all income groups with an overall mean of 3.83.
- ✓ There is a significant difference among different income group people on the factors affecting work environment among bank employees.
- ✓ Psychological stress and frustration is the most dominant factor that affects work environment among all income groups with a mean value of 3.39, and is the most dominant factor among low and middle income groups.
- ✓ Social status in the society is the most dominant factor affecting work environment among high income group people with a mean value of 3.45.

6. Suggestions

- Work environment in banks should be improved to the level of satisfaction of employees.
- Banks to start using training programs as tools of motivation.
- Banks should start using feedback of employees to the level of satisfaction of employees.
- Banks should start rewarding and recognizing employees for good work.
- Banks should actively engage employees and check their physical health on regular basis.
- Banks should conduct psychological tests of employees during induction & periodically to check for stress and frustration.

7. Conclusion

Job satisfaction can be influenced by a person's ability to complete required tasks, the level of communication in an organization, and the way management treats employees. Therefore Psychological stress and frustration should be minimized to avoid dissatisfaction. By the study we know the facing new challenges by employees are more preferable. The respondents consider the involvement & responsibility among employees, feeling of security, personal growth, pleasant work environment and recognition for creativity as a motivation for better performance. Training program, promotion opportunities, transfer to preferable locations

and co-operation & guidance of superiors also makes them to have extra motivation among employees.

8. References

1. Esra,Z. (2012). The effects of work motivation in quality of work life and A study on banking sector. 3rd International symposium on Sustainable development.
2. Singh, J., &Kaur, G. (2009). Determinants of Job satisfaction in select Indian universal banks An empirical study. *Asia-Pacific Business Review*, V(4), 43–55.#
3. Nazil A Nazir (1998), “Perceived importance of job facts and overall job satisfaction of bank employees”, *Indian journal of industrial relationship*, Vol.3.
4. Sowmya, K.R and Panchanatham,N (2011), “Factors influencing job satisfaction of banking sector employees in Chennai”. *International journal of Law and Conflict Resolution*, vol 3(5), pp.76-79.